

DO WE NEED HEALTHCARE MANAGERS IN UZBEKISTAN?

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10730031>

Annotation: This article highlights the reasons why Uzbekistan needs healthcare managers, the role of the health service administrator, and achievements when healthcare managers achieve when they start working in a hospital as a manager.

Key words: stakeholders, managerial functions, strategic expertise, leadership, organizational structures, laws and regulations, medical practices

It is common knowledge that, no business or project is done without managing. Whenever we encounter any office or organization we do see managers at the head of work. But why we should not need them in medicine? In Uzbekistan most hospitals are managed by head doctors. If we take another independent countries which have a great healthcare systems, they all do have healthcare managers that means that there is something profitable that healthcare managers do or the way they manage the whole hospital also plays an important role in healthcare system. Of course , our head doctors who are managing the hospitals are also experienced in their field , they do have high qualifications but it can only solve the problems in hospitals but can not fully contribute to the development of healthcare system . Moreover , even without managing neither medicine nor other fields can be enhanced .The position of our healthcare managers and managing in medicine plays the pivotal role in our life! A healthcare manager works on the administrative side of a healthcare facility, focusing on the business side of running a medical organization. They can work in a variety of different surroundings, including hospitals or group medical practices, as well as facilities specializing in a particular type of care, such as nursing homes. Even though these businesses provide incredibly important patient care, they must also be on top of their business responsibilities, such as finances, human resources, and marketing. The manager will help them achieve these goals. Hospital manager duties are found within hospital facilities, but they can also be found within specific clinical areas and private practices. Hospital managers take main responsibility of the entire facility, so they have quite a varied range of responsibilities. As a hospital manager, you are more likely to spend your days overseeing finances, communicating with stakeholders and investors, and ensuring compliance with laws and regulations. Professionals

choosing this field do not have to have a particular background in medicine or nursing to work in this role, although some will enter the field with this type of knowledge. While most medical and health services managers will earn a master's degree, or at least a bachelor's degree, they can have the experience needed for this role working in other administrative or clinical positions in healthcare. Health services managers bring together skills from a variety of fields of expertise. For example, they should have excellent soft skills related to communication, independence, problem-solving, and leadership. At the same time, they will need important hard skills to help them steer the technology that has become standard in many healthcare facilities. Skills and background in business management will also benefit them.

Public health management helps in putting resources to optimal use in services that deliver effective and fair healthcare to the people. It is a specialty that covers administrative and managerial functions, organizational structures, and financial systems to authorize improved health services. Responsible for providing leadership, direction, training, and management for medical operations. When we talk about operations , managers do not operate but sustain with everything which is urgent for the operation. Provides strategic expertise and guidance, and has increased accountability. Management level roles have the management and development of people as a major accountability and have direct reports.

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